

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

Target specificity of *Drosophila* PAX6 transcription factor homologs

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

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(Q1) Proposal name

Target specificity of *Drosophila* PAX6 transcription factor homologs.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

Drosophila contains two PAX6 transcription factors, ey and toy, which have distinct roles in brain development. We will identify differences in transcriptional target genes between ey and toy as possible drivers for these distinct roles using bulk RNAseq and CUT&RUN.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

The project will create non-human (*Drosophila melanogaster*) data exclusively. The data consists of high-throughput (HT) sequencing data for measuring transcript expression levels (bulk RNA-seq) or transcription factor binding profiles (CUT&RUN) with associated metadata (sample data such as transcription factor analysed, tissue, developmental stage and technical metadata such as sequence library metrics, sequencer, etc.) and data analysis.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

New primary data will be generated for both RNA-seq and CUT&RUN experiments.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

RNA-seq data: 20 samples (4 wild-type, 4 ey overexpression, 4 ey knockdown, 4 toy overexpression, 4 toy knockdown) will be sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq X Plus Series sequencer, 150bp paired-end reads to a depth of 20M reads. Results will be stored in compressed FASTQ format with a size of approximately 6GB per sample. TOTAL file size: approximately 120GB.

CUT&RUN data: 8 samples (4 ey, 4 toy) will be sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq X Plus Series sequencer, 150bp paired-end reads to a depth of 8M reads. Results will be stored in compressed FASTQ format with a size of approximately 2.4GB per sample. TOTAL file size: approximately 19.2GB.

Analysed data for RNA-seq experiments will consist of absolute (read counts) and relative (log₂ of fold change) expression levels relative to wild-type stored as tab-separated text files. For CUT&RUN experiments, the analysed data will consist of BigBED files with peak calling. TOTAL file size: less than 1GB

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Raw, intermediate and analysed data will be stored and curated on a dedicated, in-lab server (costed for in the project) with backup in the cloud (Google Drive). Raw data will be stored as compressed FASTQ (academic.oup.com/nar/article/38/6/1767/3112533). Intermediate data will be stored as bam files ([samtools.github.io/hts-specs/SAMv1.pdf](https://github.io/hts-specs/SAMv1.pdf)) and tab-separated text files. Processed data will be stored in tab-separated text files for differential gene expression and bigBED (encodeproject.org/help/file-formats/#bigbed) files for CUT&RUN experiments.

Metadata will be recorded initially in electronic lab books.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

HT sequencing data: Metadata for each experiment will be stored in MAGE-TAB format (doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-7-489) to MINSEQE standards (zenodo.org/record/5706412).

Biological metadata will be further refined (organism, strain, developmental stage, sex, tissue and genotype) and stored in Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) format.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All research data will be kept locally for a minimum of 10 years after the end of the project. Longer-term data preservation will be achieved by depositing the data to public repositories.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

All data will be available through a web interface to the dedicated server. In addition, data will be available through the public repository ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress).

Analysis pipelines will be made available through GitHub.

(Q10) When will data be available?

All data will be made available upon publication or within three years of generation of the dataset, whichever comes first.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

HT sequencing data and associated metadata will be deposited to ArrayExpress. Data will be MINSEQE compliant. Unique DOIs for each dataset, as generated by the online repository, will be listed in any publication that describes or uses the data.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

Metadata required for appropriate reuse and the use of interoperable data formats (MINSEQE) will accompany all data submitted to the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress).

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

All data will be made available upon publication or within three years of generation of the dataset, whichever comes first, with no further restrictions or delays anticipated.

(Q14) Secondary use

Researchers studying transcription factor specificity, especially of PAX6 transcription factors in other model organisms or in humans, will benefit from this dataset.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

The University is ISO 27001 certified.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

Only model organism data will be generated.

(Q17) Capabilities

The university provides unlimited storage capacity on Google Drive as well as access to Arkivum for long-term storage of large datasets.

Furthermore, the university provides a free platform to share the intellectual products of the university freely and openly with the staff and students of the university or with the global academic and public community (RADAR).

As indicated in the Justification of Resources, a server has been costed in the project to provide medium-term storage and analysis capabilities.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

Data management plan implementation, auditing and revision is the responsibility of the PI and will be a recurring topic during the weekly team meetings.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

Environmental sustainability at the University is guided by the framework of our externally certified ISO14001:2015 Environmental Management System (EMS). The EMS enforces an environmental policy that sets out our principles and goals, and is supported by a series of strategies outlining our key vision, drivers and objectives for each key aspect of environmental sustainability. The university also takes part in the LEAF initiative to reduce the carbon emissions of research labs and create an environment that supports research quality

(Q20) Responsibilities

Person responsible for:

- **Study-wide data management:** Unnamed PDRA (new hire for this project)
- **Metadata creation:** Unnamed PDRA (new hire for this project)
- **Data security:** PI
- **Quality assurance of data:** PI and University Research Data Manager